

Geo-Distributed Simulation and Verification Infrastructure for safe train Galileo-based positioning

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Abstract: The work shows the high level concept and methodology followed for designing a geo-distributed simulation and verification infrastructure connecting remotely GNSS excellence centres and ERTMS/ETCS laboratories to evaluate the GNSS performances in the railway environment. Proper methodology and tools are adopted to simulate GNSS behaviour in different railway scenarios in nominal or in presence of global and local hazards.

Particularly, the test-bed main goals are: i) achieving a realistic characterization of the environment in terms of railway and GNSS infrastructures able to evaluate the performances and properties of some fail-safe train positioning components in nominal and fault conditions; ii) defining a common test process framework for zero on-site testing instead of testing on-site saving effort and time.

The test-bed offers the unique advantage to stress the global system in presence of very rare GNSS fault events instead of performing long and expensive measurement campaigns on field for detecting them and analysing their impact on ETCS. The work will show its description and the methodology adopted for its design and implementation.

1 Introduction

With the "Smart, green and integrated transport" challenge, the European Union intends to boost the competitiveness of the European transport industries and achieve a European transport system that is resource efficient, climate-and-environment-friendly, safe and seamless for the benefit of all citizens, economy and society. One of the tools for such an ambition is to boost innovative and cost-efficient technologies and systems for railway signalling and automated driving while, at the same time, reaching a level of safety consistent with methods and standards applicable in all railway segments. To achieve developments in railway systems, the Shift2Rail JU annual workplan has focused on several work axes among which:

- the development of innovative and advanced control, command and communication systems, taking advantage of new technologies and practices, including the use of satellite positioning technologies;
- a contribution to the zero-on-site testing objective with the definition of a system test architecture, as well as the specification of a standardized method to derive and describe test cases.

The European Union Agency for Railways detailed in a report on the longer-term perspective for the evolution of ERTMS (European Railway Traffic Management System) dated from December 2015 that satellite positioning is one of the "game-changers" for improving the operational performances and reducing the cost of the overall system.

In past research projects, several applications for GNSS-based ERTMS have been defined, for example for improving the positioning accuracy of the ERTMS odometry (GRAIL, GRAIL-2) or for replacing Eurobalises with virtual ones thanks to GNSS (RUNE [1], and more recently in 3InSat [2] ERSAT-EAV [3], or RHINOS [4]).

However, some crucial issues still need investigation [4], among which the characterization of GNSS effects in the railway environment and their impact on the Virtual Balise (VB) placement. ERSAT GGC on-going project aims at defining a methodology for GNSS quality reception characterization along the track. The project will provide a track area classification with three classes: suitable, not suitable and "to be further investigated" for GNSS-based VB placement [5].

In this paper, we will show the features of a geo-distributed simulation and verification infrastructure addressing two important aspects and performed in the framework of the Gate4Rail project:

1. the characterization of the railway local environment as a component of GNSS performances: the description of scenarios and railway surroundings will support the evaluation of performances and properties of some fail-safe train positioning components, strongly influenced by global and local effects. It aims at defining a proper methodology for GNSS characterization considering the railway propagation conditions in nominal and fault conditions.
2. the development of a dedicated laboratory system architecture to simulate much more faults in the system than could be ever tested in the field. By adopting it, the outage probability in field due to these errors can be reduced, increasing the infrastructure availability.

An architecture capable of testing ERTMS trackside and on-board signalling systems using GNSS for train positioning in a common GNSS and ETCS (European Train Control System) infrastructure, with the interfaces connecting remotely the testing partners' labs will be shown.

2 Concept

The work aims at showing the first distributed infrastructure in the world connecting existing European laboratories with a deep knowledge and expertise in GNSS and ERTMS domains.

Particularly, they are:

1. RadioLabs laboratory that has different high precision GNSS receivers (in particular Septentrio AsteRx Receivers with PolaNt-X MF antennas used in different measurements campaigns for collecting real GNSS data on railway tracks in Italy (in Sardinia, along the Cagliari-San Gavino railway track, and on the Parma – La Spezia Pontremolese line) and a digital beamforming platform based on SDR equipment (National Instruments NI USRP-2943R) with an antenna array specifically designed for anti-jam and anti-spoof detection and mitigation. Moreover, RadioLabs has designed and developed a simulation tool named VIRGILIO (Virtual InstRuments for GNSS AugmentatIon and LocalizatION), that is a complete multi-constellation and multi-frequency software simulator for the GNSS LDSs for rail. It supports H/W in the loop simulation and has high scalability through distributed simulation in cloud environment.
2. IFSTTAR has acquired experience in multipath and in particular Non Line of Sight (NLOS) detection. The tools own by IFSTTAR rely on sky fish-eye image processing and GNSS satellite position simulators [6]. IFSTTAR has access to GNSS measurements databases coming from previous rail measurement campaigns with reference trajectories that will be processed for error modelling.
3. RFI Sardinia real Test bed that is currently the only one in Europe fully dedicated to the GNSS application in the railway by using a commercial line. In this way, it will ensure the possibility to support physical test environments too. It could be used as benchmark for comparing the performance achievable with only virtual testing.
4. M3 Systems Belgium has developed a complete GNSS dedicated test bed product named STELLA[®]. STELLA is a highly versatile solution for GNSS testing, enabling both the simulation of GNSS signals and the record and playback of real signals collected on the field. The simulation function provides support to account for various errors that can affect GNSS performances (such as the impact of the propagation of the signal through the atmosphere, or clock errors, but also local errors such as multi-path). GNSS vulnerability to interferences and attacks can also be tested using STELLA.
5. GUIDE is a testing laboratory specialized in characterizing the performances of Location Determination Systems (LDSs) in terrestrial environments, where GNSS measurements may be unstable. Two test methodologies are implemented: one to assess “typical” performances such as accuracy and availability, and the other for “critical” performances related to integrity. GUIDE is implementing the metrological technique, so called “Record and Replay” to provide a thorough analysis.
Results of his study are also intended to be used to enhance the navigation map and to anticipate potential errors caused by the environment. Relying on this data, the onboard positioning system should be able to improve its accuracy and to raise its level of integrity.
6. CEDEX ETCS/ERTMS laboratory is an accredited lab for testing ERTMS components such as EVCs (Euro Vital Computers) and Eurobalises, and also performs testing of railway lines. CEDEX lab has an important role in the testing of Spanish real lines before placing in service, allowing the significant reduction of on-site testing time and resources, as the real lines can be debugged in advance in the laboratory environment.
7. INECO has, over the years, accumulated significant experience in ERTMS definition and deployment and in GNSS application studies and final implementation. In this context, has developed a simulation tool to analyze satellite coverage (LOS and geometry) for GPS and Galileo constellations along any railway track and during configurable time frames. The distinguishing feature is the use of Digital Surface Models to create a 3D model of track environment and resulting in a powerful and cost saving solution for GNSS quality pre-assessment during planning phase and pre-tactical railway operation phase.

Connecting the facilities and laboratories above listed and described, the geo-distributed simulation and verification infrastructure will have three main assets:

1. GNSS laboratories for generating and simulating GNSS signals including the global and local hazards to evaluate the performance of GNSS-based LDS inserted in ETCS;

2. a block specifically designed to provide to the GNSS laboratory the information related to the train positioning, as well as the environment details of the selected railway track (collected for example through previous line characterizations);
3. an entire ERTMS testing environment for performance evaluation of real ETCS OBU (On Board Unit) including RBC (Radio Block Center) and connected to the two previous ones. In particular, it will be responsible for sending the train movement information to the 2 and receives the GNSS-based OBU signals or virtual balises triggering from 1.

One of most important intrinsic advantages of this solution is to facilitate the process of characterization campaigns along a selected railway line without intensive acquisition campaigns on operational lines. In the hypothesis of a railway company (signalling company, railway operator) that aims at characterizing of a GNSS-based LDS in the ETRMS/ETCS context in specific environmental situations (multipath, EMI), a rolling stock equipped with a set of dedicated hardware must be deployed and run along the targeted railway line. For that action, there are several implications time and resources consuming: hardware physical installation feasibility (such as the analysis of electromagnetic compatibility due to eventual interferences with existing instrumentation), hardware installation authorization request, identified hardware procurement, installation and uninstallation at the end of campaign, considering all man hours required for the entire process.

Moreover, if there are some H/W or S/W change due to obsolescence, the test bed allows to generate the movement of a train along a real line (according to ERTMS rules) obtaining high-fidelity ground-truth avoiding on field acquisition and saving money and time.

Finally, the test bed allows verifying the global system (GNSS and railway) response in presence of rare events instead of executing a significant number of trials on field (expecting to face such events during the trial). By means of a virtualized simulation and verification test bed, GATE4Rail allows evaluating the system performance injecting GNSS faults at both global (satellite clock or ephemeris error, ionospheric degradation) and local (multipath, electromagnetic interference, jamming, spoofing and meaconing (direct and network)) levels also through Monte-Carlo simulations. In this case, by using techniques like importance sampling, one can stress the system and perform the sensitivity analysis even in presence of very rare events, not likely to occur in nominal conditions.

In order to support the development of the simulation environment and to ensure interoperability of the solutions and tools provided by the various laboratories, the test bed implementation will rely on the implementation of a Model Based System Engineering (MBSE) approach. The advantage of such approach is twofold. On the one side, it will ensure interoperability of the solutions provided by the various laboratories. On the other side, it will also ensure that the simulation infrastructure can be maintained and that it can evolve in the future. There are several options to implement MBSE approach. In this context it is proposed to implement a methodology named “Architecture Analysis and Design Integrated Approach”. This methodology had been initiated by Thales in 2007 before being standardized as part of the Association Française de Normalisation (AFNOR) in 2018. In usual development practices, most of the time, developers mainly focus on the definition of requirements, their allocation to the system component, and their traceability. Doing so, constraints related to system integration, product line management, safety, performance and feasibility are not clearly identified in the process. To fix this issue, and to break the ‘walls’ between different engineering specializations, the proposed method rather focuses on functional analysis, system design, justification of architectural choices and verification steps. In addition, the design takes into account not only the functional point of view, but also other ones, which affect the definition and breakdown of the system. Then, the non-functional properties expected from the system solution are also formalized in 'viewpoints'. Each viewpoint captures constraints that the system should face or meet. Then the architecture model is automatically analyzed to verify that it meets these constraints, thanks to dedicated expert rules (performance computation, resource consumption, safety or security barriers, etc.). This analysis can be done very early in the development cycle, detecting design issues as soon as possible ("early validation").

The Architecture Analysis and Design Integrated Approach is defined in 4 main phases as it follows (see Figure 1):

1. *"Operational Analysis Model"*

The first step focuses on analyzing the customer needs and goals, expected missions and activities, far beyond System requirements. This is expected to ensure good adequacy of system definition with regards to its real operational use – and identify the Integration, Verification, Validation, and Qualification (IVVQ) conditions.

This phase aims at the definition of an "operational architecture" describing and structuring this need, in terms of actors/users, their operational capabilities and activities, operational use scenarios providing dimensioning parameters and operational constraints including safety, security, lifecycle, etc.

2. *"System Functional and non-functional need model"*

The second step focuses on the system itself, in order to define how it can satisfy the former operational need, along with its expected behavior and qualities:

- system functions to be supported and related exchanges;
- non-functional constraints (safety and security);
- performances allocated to system boundary;
- role sharing and interactions between system and operators.

To do this, a first early system architecture (architectural design model) is sketched from system functional need; then requirements are examined against this architecture in order to evaluate their consistency.

The second step objective is to provide a system functional need description, interoperability and interaction with the users and external systems (functions, exchanges plus non-functional constraints), and system requirements.

3. *"Logical Architecture Model"*

The third step intends to identify the system parts (hereafter called components), their contents, relationships and properties, excluding implementation or technical/technological issues. This constitutes the system logical architecture. In order to have this breakdown in components stable in further steps, all major [non-functional] constraints (safety, security, performance, IVV, Cost, non-technical, etc.) are taken into account, and compared to each other's to find the best compromise between them. This method is described as "Viewpoints-driven", let viewpoints be the formalization of the way in which these constraints impact on the system architecture. Outputs of this step consist of the selected logical architecture: components and interfaces definition, including formalization of all viewpoints and the way in which they are taken into account in the components design. Since the architecture has to be validated against need, links with requirements and operational scenarios are also produced.

4. *"Development of System Architecture – Physical Architecture"*

The fourth step has the same intents as logical architecture building, except that it defines the "final" architecture of the system at this level of engineering, ready to develop (by lower engineering levels). Therefore, it introduces rationalization, architectural patterns, new technical services and components, and allows the logical architecture to evolve according to the implementation, technical and technological constraints and choices (at this level of engineering). Note that the same "Viewpoints-driven" method, as for logical architecture building, is used for physical architecture definition. This final step aims at providing the selected physical architecture: components to be produced, including formalization of all viewpoints and the way in which they are taken into account in the components design. Links with requirements and operational scenarios are also produced. This approach based on models and functional analysis, and use-case centric will ensure the interoperability of the simulation tools/means of the various laboratories, and will make the whole system easy to maintain and to be further modified (update/upgrade/addition of new functionalities). As part of the first phase of the MBSE approach, the use cases will be defined in a structured way using appropriate modelling languages such as Unified Modeling Language (UML) or Systems Modeling Language (SysML) for instance. These models will then enable automatic generation of simulation scenarios, their automatic run, automatic computation of the associated Key Performance Indicators and to finalize automatic benchmark of these KPIs with the use case performance requirements. In other words, proper capture and definition of the use cases, by using appropriate modelling tools, enables the complete automation of the simulation process. Of course, this also implies that relevant constraints have been taken into account for the definition of the simulation infrastructure (which will be made easier thanks the MBSE approach). In parallel with this MBSE approach, it is also proposed to define and implement a methodology (and the associated tools) in order to enable to perform tests in an automated way and to analyze their results

automatically as well. The key idea is to ensure that the simulation infrastructure will meet the requirements of system integrators and assessors, thanks to a continuous integration development approach, automated repetition of test cases and automated evaluation of the test results. Also, safety aspects (and their approval by independent assessors) will be taken into account in this activity. To do so, it is proposed to use a use-case centric approach.

Figure 1. Architecture Analysis and Design Integrated Approach phases (source: <http://www.polarsys.org/capella/arcadia.html>)

3 Architecture

The simulation and verification infrastructure consists of five following main modules (see Figure 2):

Module #1: Emulated Moving Train

It is a Railway Traffic Generator represented in Figure 2 through the grey block and is implemented through the CEDEX ETCS/ERTMS laboratory that generates the railway traffic. Moreover, this block interacts with the Balise detected trigger (described in detail below) that states if the train is passed over a VB located in the route and delivers the Balise reference Identification.

Module #2: Mission Control System & Train Dynamics:

This node (in orange shaded) that processes the information received from the traffic generator (position and speed profile of the specific train, etc ...) and translates them into a set of information usable by GNSS infrastructure. In particular, the **Mission Control System** takes the input from the **Global Track info** (a sort of GIS of the section with track map, obstacles, etc., potentially external and made available by a specific provider in the future) and from the traffic generator and defines the route of the train. Particularly, the main outputs are:

1. subset of Track database info
 - a. *Local track info* (information about the portion of track nearby the train);
 - b. *VB locations* (locations of nearby virtual balises);
 - c. *Environmental info* (subset of information regarding the features of the local track surrounding environment such as orography, obstacles, tall buildings, presence of well-known electromagnetic sources along the line (presence of airports radars and MLS, television and radio stations));
2. Location of the train at the first epoch;
3. Simulation time window (temporal extension of the simulation);
4. Movement profile (e.g. constant speed, speed at first epoch, target speed). Finally, the *Mission Control System* block is planned to connect the nodes on a geographically distributed network and to be a master processing node that performs the function of an orchestrator to realise the test process in an automatic way.

The **Train Dynamics** block takes as inputs the 1a, 2, 3, 4 of the previous blocks and generates the movement trajectory of the train. Particularly, the output consists of **Ground truth info** that is a list of train positions and time. The schematic overview of the main inputs/outputs of the Mission Control System & Train Dynamics block is depicted in Figure 2.

Module #3: GNSS Signals Generation

This block (shaded node in blue) is responsible for the generation of synthetic GNSS signals and observables both in nominal and fault conditions. Global hazards will be generated based on historical rare faults recorded on satellites ephemeris and clocks or based on synthetic faults. Local hazards such as multipath, GNSS signal blockage or unintentional and intentional interferences will also be made available for the scenario definition. They will be extracted from real database and real examples of local events.

A direct connection with external repositories (since some institutions have historical fault databases) including both global and local GNSS rare faults will be foreseen in the different releases of virtualized simulation and verification infrastructure. Concerning local hazards that affects the railway environment, multipath and obstructions, the scope is to better represent their effects on the following parameters: satellites signals availability due to obstructions; C/N0 attenuation due to the surrounding environment; PVT errors related to pseudoranges and phase measurements due to multipath. This will improve the representativeness of the GNSS in the railway scenarios of the interest (regional, urban and suburban and freight lines).

Particularly, the blue module takes as input the ground truth, environmental information and the AIMN (including EGNOS and D-GPS (Differential-GPS) /RTK (Real Time Kinematics) (according to 2-Tier approach [7]) or one of them in modular way) information (it can include at least the positions of the Reference Stations (RSs)) if the adoption of the augmentation is foreseen. The outputs of this module are raw data (pseudoranges, carrier phase, Doppler shift, Carrier to Noise Ratio (C/N0)).

Figure 2. Overall GATE4Rail Logic Scheme

This block allows a direct injection of hazards in I/Q (In-phase /Quadrature) samples or in the RF (Radio-Frequency) domain. In that case, this block will include a GNSS receiver (used for benchmark too). Otherwise, you can synthesize through this block the global and local hazards by injecting them directly into the raw data domain without the need of RF signals generation.

Module #4: GNSS Augmentation and On-Board Unit Module

This module represents the GNSS-based train positioning unit. It includes a GNSS-based OBU and a conventional (EGNOS or DGPS/RTK) AIMN. A two-tier AIMN architecture (EGNOS plus DGPS/RTK) is also supported. In this way, one can evaluate and test the performance of the whole system in terms of accuracy, integrity and availability (according to the philosophy of modular-based design) then comparing different alternatives for both augmentation network and OBU. Through OBU, different ad hoc techniques for multipath detection and exclusion and Receiver Autonomous Integrity Monitoring (RAIM) can be tested. These hybridizations could be completed by a navigation map intended to weight the confidence given to the implemented sensors. This module processes the input data and provides PVT and Protection Levels.

Module #5: Virtual Balise Trigger module

This mustard-colored block detects the passage over a VB and notifies this event. Particularly its output is the passage trigger with the balise reference ID. The inputs are the VB positions and the PVT estimation.

4 Conclusions and perspectives

At the time of writing the paper, the project reaches its mid-term. Currently, the test-bed is in the phase of detailed design of the interfaces among the different modules. In the final version of the work, we will show an example of test-bed operation simulating some representative rail scenarios and verifying the performance of VB-based GNSS w.r.t the defined requirements of SIL-4 accuracy train positioning.

5 Acknowledgment

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